

Preface to the first edition - QIJMHS

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EDITORIAL

It is our pleasure to write this editorial for the inaugural edition of “Quest International Journal of Medical and Health Sciences” (QIJMHS). The vision of Quest International University Perak (QIUP) is to promote and facilitate research activities and publications. QIUP is a private research-led University established under the Higher Educational Institutions Act 555 on 12th June 2008 in Perak and is owned by Global Integrated Training Associates Sdn. Bhd. (formerly known as Blair Education Services Sdn. Bhd) in which the State Government of Perak has an equity participation along with the QI Group. This Journal is launched with the objective of sharing the research advancements that have been made in the past few years and which are on-going in the fields of Medicine, Pharmacy, Biomedicine, and Biotechnology. The main objective of the QIJMHS is to inspire researchers to publish their work through the internet. Our focus is on Physicians, Scientists, Dentists, Nurses and allied health science workers in South East Asian countries. These are the people who are exposed to management of a broad spectrum of diseases and have a wealth of knowledge to share.

The online publication of their valuable clinical and research experiences will benefit the healthcare professionals in various fields. We started QIJMHS with a vision of publishing all research papers in the field of medicine and health sciences under a single platform. This will help researchers from all these fields to publish in one journal and our open access policy will help free access to these articles.

The value of knowledge is only worthy when it is shared, and of course, taking into consideration that there is no conflict of interest. The enormous growth of the internet and the open access policy of this journal helps in the sharing of information. This is for the further advancement in every field by conducting more research and ultimately contributing to the welfare of mankind.

We are very grateful to Dato’ Sri Dr. Vijay Eswaran, the Chairman of Quest International University Perak for his support. We are also proud to have Mr. Nicholas Goh Kaw Chin, our Chief Operating Officer, and En. Muhammad Muammar Gadaffi Omar, the Registrar as our patrons. We extend our gratitude to Professor Dato’ Dr. Raman Narayanasamy, the Vice-Chancellor, for his support and valuable suggestions from the very beginning and also to our dedicated team of renowned clinicians, researchers and educators of Faculty of Medicine QIUP, from various countries such as Malaysia, India, Pakistan, Myanmar and

Bangladesh. The strong endeavour of the editorial board members made this accomplishment achievable. We would like to thank our peer reviewers for their valuable time, comments and suggestions. We pledge to upkeep the quality and transparency of research. Currently, we are accepting editorials, letters to the editor, short communications, current research trends, case reports and case series, original research, student research and review articles (narrative and systematic). We wish to establish this journal, as one of the best by maintaining proper ethical guidelines, scientific quality, and technical proficiency. Our English language editor ensures the correctness of the language, and our web editor assists on the technical aspects. We also pledge to index our journal in internationally recognized databases. However, this accomplishment can only be fulfilled with your contribution to the future issues. It would be extremely remiss on our side unless we acknowledge the involvement and express our gratitude to the many individuals whose active cooperation and help made our journal come up with a progressive vision.

Regards

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Competing interests

None declared.

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